

HISLAND 2026

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE “HISTORICAL
AND CULTURAL LANDSCAPES”

PROGRAMME

TSU, HISLAND RESEARCH TEAM | TBILISI, GEORGIA | FEBRUARY 14 -15, 2026

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE - HISTORICAL AND CULTURAL LANDSCAPES (HISLAND 2026)

February 14-15, 2026 | Tbilisi | Georgia

VENUE/ADDRESS

Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University (TSU)

1 Ilia Chavtchavadze Avenue

Academic Building I

0179 Tbilisi, Georgia.

41°42'35.75"N; 44°46'41.73"E

ORGANISERS: The HISLAND Research Team (Project #FR-22-3989; Principal Investigator: Dr. Roman Maisuradze), Ivane Javakhishvili Tbilisi State University (TSU).

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PROGRAMME SCHEDULE

14 February 2026 | Day One | Auditorium 115

Time	Registration and Opening
09:00 – 09:40	Registration
09:40 – 10:00	Opening Remarks

Time	Thematic Session 1: Landscape Archaeology Chair: <i>Gia Chilingarashvili</i>
10:00 – 10:15	<i>Saba Jokhadze</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Ivane Javakbshvili Tbilisi State University, Tbilisi, Georgia</i> ▪ <i>Georgian National Museum</i> Rivers Networks: Landscape Archaeology as a Tool for Research Neolithic Exchange
10:15 – 10:30	<i>Vazha Sadradze, Merab Dzneladze, Tamta Tchovelidze</i> , <i>Department of Archaeology and History of Georgia, Faculty of Social Sciences, Georgian Technical University, Tbilisi, Georgia</i> A Newly Discovered Cemetery on the Shore of the Tbilisi Sea
10:30 – 10:45	<i>Aleksandre Rusetsky</i> , <i>Georgian Technical University, Tbilisi, Georgia</i> The Potential of the Gonio – Apsaros Landscape for Reconstructing the Multiriver Model of <i>Phasis</i>
10:45 – 11:00	<i>Gia Chilingarashvili</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ <i>Ivane Javakbshvili Tbilisi State University, Tbilisi, Georgia</i> ▪ <i>Georgian National Museum</i> The Occupational History of the Samtskhe Region: Visibility and Bias in Archaeological Survey

11:10 - 12:00 Coffee Break

Time	Thematic Session 2: Socio-Economic, Political, and Media Landscape Chair: <i>Marekb Devidze</i>
12:00 – 12:15	<i>Lela Mamaladze</i> , <i>Faculty of Social Sciences, Sulkhani-Saba Orbeliani University, Tbilisi, Georgia</i> The Digital Economy and the New Geography of Employment: The Impact of Remote Work on Spatial Population Concentration

12:15 – 12:30	Mariam Vashakidze, Ketik Khizanishvili , Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, Department of Journalism and Mass Communication, Ivane Javakbshvili Tbilisi State University, Tbilisi, Georgia The Georgian Press on the Establishment of Tbilisi State University – Based on 1918 Publications
12:30 – 12:45	Tamar Devidze, Marek Devidze, George Mamulaishvili , Institute of Conflictology, Ivane Javakbshvili Tbilisi State University, Tbilisi, Georgia Meskhetian Turks: Deportation and Repatriation Issues (A Historical Overview)

12:45 – 14:00 Lunch Break

Time	WORKSHOP 1
14:00 – 15:00	Harry Rogge <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ EUROGEO - European Association of Geographers – Member of the Board (Bruges, Belgium) ▪ Council of Europe - Official delegate to the International Conference of NGO's (Strasbourg, France) ▪ KNAG – Royal Dutch Geographical Society – member <p>EUROPE – Maps, Borders and the European Landscape Convention</p>

Time	Thematic Session 3: Landscape Architecture, Heritage, Land Use, and Planning Chair: <i>Rusudan Mirzikashvili</i>
15:00 – 15:15	Elene Panchulidze , International Relations Department, Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, Ivane Javakbshvili Tbilisi State University, Tbilisi, Georgia Soviet Architecture as a Tool for Spreading Ideology and Propaganda
15:15 – 15:30	Rusudan Mirzikashvili , Newcastle University, Newcastle Upon Tyne, United Kingdom Landscapes, Heritage-Making and Social Stratification
15:30 – 15:45	Antal Szántay , Corvinus University of Budapest, Budapest, Hungary Land Use in 18th-century Hungary and Croatia: Some Considerations on Sources and Methods (Online)
15:45 – 16:00	Tinatín Meparishvili , School of Architecture, Planning and Landscape, Newcastle University, Newcastle Upon Tyne, United Kingdom Touristification, Gentrification, and Temporal Sense of Place in Rome's Historic Urban Landscape (Online)

Time	Thematic Session 4: Physical, Environmental and Medical Geography, Landscape Ecology Chair: <i>Tamar Khardziani</i>
16:00 – 16:15	Maia Chubinidze , <i>Department of Biology, Faculty of Exact and Natural Science, Ivane Javakbshvili Tbilisi State University, Tbilisi, Georgia</i> Study of bee (<i>Hymenoptera, Apoidea</i>) diversity in the major landscape types of the Kojori area (Tbilisi surroundings)
16:15 – 16:30	Mariam Beradze, Nikoloz Gabroshvili , <i>Faculty of Medicine, Ivane Javakbshvili Tbilisi State University, Tbilisi, Georgia</i> Historical Therapeutic Spaces in Georgia as a Cultural Landscape of Health
16:30 – 16:45	Zurab Seperteladze, Eter Davitaia, George Gaprindashvili, Tamar Aleksidze , <i>Department of Geography, Faculty of Exact and Natural Sciences, Ivane Javakbshvili Tbilisi State University, Tbilisi, Georgia</i> Landscape Energetics - the Main Parameter Determining the Natural Resource Potential of Anthropogenic Complexes
16:45 – 17:00	Tamar Khardziani , <i>Department of Geography, Faculty of Exact and Natural Sciences, Ivane Javakbshvili Tbilisi State University, Tbilisi, Georgia</i> TERRA RIPARIA – Application of a Landscape Ecology Framework to Assess Riparian Forest Fragmentation
17:00 – 17:15	Closing Remarks

15 February 2026 | Day Two | Auditorium 115

10:00 -10:30	Welcome Coffee
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Time	Thematic Session 5: Historical and Cultural Landscapes, Landscape Education Chair: <i>Roman Maisuradze</i>
10:30 – 10:45	Armine Zurabyan , <i>Department of Service, Yerevan State University, Yerevan, Armenia</i> Josep Vila-Subirós , <i>Director, Cultural and Natural Heritage Campus. Research Group on Socio-Environmental Change (SAMBI) University of Girona, Girona, Spain</i> Hovik Sayadyan , <i>Faculty of Geography and Geology, Yerevan State University, Yerevan, Armenia</i> The Cultural-Historical Landscapes of Armenia: Long-Term Human–Nature Interactions as a Basis for Contemporary Sustainability Approaches

10:45 – 11:00	Maia Bliadze , <i>European University, Tbilisi, Georgia</i> Teaching Historical and Cultural Landscapes in Geography Lessons: Theoretical Foundations and Pedagogical Practice
11:00 – 11:15	Bezhan Khorava , <i>Tamaz Beradze Institute of Georgian Studies, University of Georgia, Tbilisi, Georgia</i> Ketevan Margiani , <i>Sokhumi State University, Tbilisi, Georgia</i> Rusudan Ioseliani , <i>Ilia State University, Tbilisi, Georgia</i> Roman Maisuradze , <i>Ivane Javakbshvili Tbilisi State University, Tbilisi, Georgia</i> Historical-Geographical Analysis of the Geographical Names of the Dali Gorge According to Historiographic and Cartographic Sources of the 19th-20th Centuries
11:15 – 11:30	Aleksandre Inashvili , <i>Department of Geography, Faculty of Exact and Natural Sciences, Ivane Javakbshvili Tbilisi State University, Tbilisi, Georgia</i> Planning of one of the islands of the Vltava River and the surrounding area (Troja Basin and Královská Obora Stromovka)
11:30 – 11:45	Giorgi Abramishvili , Saba Darbaidze , <i>Department of Geography, Faculty of Exact and Natural Sciences, Ivane Javakbshvili Tbilisi State University, Tbilisi, Georgia</i> Geographical Study of the Landmarks of the Settlements of Dmanisi Municipality
11:45 – 12:00	Discussion / Q&A

12:00 – 13:00 Lunch Break

Time	WORKSHOP 2
13:00 – 13:30	Roman Maisuradze , Tamar Khardziani , Gia Chilingarashvili , <i>Ivane Javakbshvili Tbilisi State University, Tbilisi, Georgia</i> Historical and Cultural Landscapes of Samtskhe-Javakheti (HISLAND Project Results)

13:30 – 13:40 REFLECTIONS AND CLOSING REMARKS